

N-Hydroxy-N-p-Chlorophenyl-N'-(2,5-Dimethyl) Phenyl-p-Toluamide Hydrochloride as an Analytical Reagent for Gravimetric Determination of Copper**

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Manuscript received 15 February 1978, accepted 10 April 1978

N-Hydroxy-N-p-Chlorophenyl-N'-(2, 5-dimethyl) phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride is proposed as a new sensitive and highly selective reagent for the gravimetric determination of copper(II). The thermally stable and directly weighable buff coloured copper complex of the reagent having the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{OCl})_2$ gets quantitatively precipitated in the pH range 3.7-11.0. Many foreign ions including Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} and WO_4^{2-} can coexist during the determination without any adverse effect. The infrared spectral studies of the reagent and the copper complex has been made. The method has been applied to various copper alloys.

RECENT communications from this laboratory have shown that N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines, I, possessing a new type of function

-N(OH)-C=N- are valuable reagents for carrying out gravimetric¹⁻³ and spectrophotometric⁴⁻⁷ determination of a large number of transition metal ions. In connection with our studies on synthesis and analytical applications of N,N'-disubstituted hydroxyamidines, this paper reports the newly synthesised reagent, N-hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,5-dimethyl)phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride as a highly selective reagent for gravimetric determination of copper(II). The proposed reagent quantitatively precipitates buff coloured copper complex in the pH range 3.7-11.0. The complex possessing a small copper content (8.034%) can be safely dried at 110-170° within 30 min and directly weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{OCl})_2$. The proposed method offers the advantages of simplicity, rapidity and selectivity. So far as sensitivity and selectivity are concerned, the present method can be favourably compared with all the established methods⁸⁻¹⁷.

Experimental

Apparatus: The infrared spectra of the reagent and its copper complex were recorded as mulls in hexachlorobutadiene (3700-2000 cm^{-1} and 1500-1300 cm^{-1}) and nujol (2000-1500 cm^{-1} and 1300-

600 cm^{-1}) on a Perkin-Elmer 221 spectrophotometer equipped with sodium chloride optics. The pH of the solutions were adjusted with dilute acetic acid, ammonium acetate and dilute ammonia and measured with a Systronic pH meter Type 322.

Reagent: N-Hydroxy-N-p-chlorophenyl-N'-(2,5-dimethyl) Phenyl-p-toluamide Hydrochloride: The reagent was prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of N-(2,5-dimethyl) phenyl-p-toluidoyl chloride and N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine in ether at 0-5° following the method of Deb and Mishra¹⁸. The resulting white crystals of the ligand were crystallised from minimum volume of absolute alcohol containing a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid (B.D.H.A.R.). White shining crystals of the compound melted at 166°. Yield; 65%. (Found: C, 66.20; H, 5.68; N, 6.79%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{OCl}$: C, 65.83; H, 5.48; N, 6.98%). A 1% solution of the reagent in 90% ethyl alcohol was used for precipitation purposes.

Copper(II) solution: A stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving copper metal (B.D.H., AnalaR) in dilute nitric acid and the solution boiled to expel oxides of nitrogen. The metal content of this solution was determined gravimetrically employing salicylaldehyde¹⁹.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grade.

Procedure: A suitable aliquot of the solution containing 2-25 mg of copper(II) was diluted to 125 ml with distilled water in a 400 ml beaker. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 3.7-11.0 with acetic acid, ammonium acetate or ammonia and the solution was heated to 50-60°. To this, was

** Presented at Annual Convention of Chemists-1977 held at Jaipur.

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added the reagent solution (3 ml of 1% reagent solution per 2 mg of copper) with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The precipitated buff coloured copper complex was digested for about 20 min over a boiling water bath. The solution, while still hot was filtered through a preweighed G-3 sintered crucible. The complex was washed with hot water followed by hot 30% ethanol till the washings gave no colour with ferric chloride. The copper complex was dried at 110-120° to constant weight and weighed as Cu(C₂₂H₂₀N₂OCl)₂. Gravimetric factor is 0.08034. The results of these determinations are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE-1 DETERMINATION OF COPPER(II)
pH, 3.9±0.1

Copper taken (mg)	Weight of copper complex (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Rel. error %
1.20	14.8	1.19	-0.83
2.40	29.8	2.39	-0.41
5.00	69.1	4.99	-0.20
12.00	149.4	12.00	Nil
20.00	249.1	20.01	+0.05
25.00	311.6	25.03	+0.12

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complex : The buff coloured copper complex is insoluble in water, ethanol and methanol and slightly soluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and dioxane. The results of copper and nitrogen analysis suggest the composition of the chelate to be Cu(C₂₂H₂₀N₂OCl)₂ (Found : Cu, 8.03 ; N, 7.01% Calcd. Cu, 8.03 ; N, 7.08%). The examination of the infrared spectra of the ligand revealed three strong bands at 2450

(=N⁺-H), 1610(C=N⁺) and 950 cm⁻¹(N-O). The

band due to =N⁺-H stretching is absent in the spectra of the copper complex. This suggests the deprotonation of the charged azomethine nitrogen atom during complex formation. Thus, the liberated free base produces copper(II) complex probably by forming a Cu-O bond (through the hydroxyloxygen) and coordination takes place through the formation of a Cu-N=C type of bond. This view, that the azomethine nitrogen atom provides the coordination site is also favoured by the fact that the C=N⁺ frequency of the ligand is lowered in the complex (1570 cm⁻¹). The formation of Cu-O-N is also evident from the displacement of N-O stretching frequency of the ligand to 960 cm⁻¹ in the complex.

Effect of pH and amount of reagent : The precipitation of the copper complex commenced at pH 2.2 and was quantitative between pH values of 3.7-11.0. A slight excess of the reagent to exceed 1 : 2 metal to reagent ratio was found to be sufficient for complete precipitation of the metal complex. A large excess of the reagent showed no adverse effect on the determination and can be washed out

very easily with ethanol in which the complex is practically insoluble. Thus, an excess of 900 mg of the reagent in a final volume of 150 ml was found to have no interfering effect on the determination of 12.00 mg of copper.

Effect of masking agents : High concentrations of masking agents such as thiourea, triethanolamine, citric acid, tartaric acid and fluoride caused no harm to the precipitation and determination of copper. However, in presence of excess EDTA copper was completely masked.

Influence of foreign ions : A known amount of cation or anion was mixed with a fixed amount of copper (12.00 mg) and the determination was carried out at pH 3.7-6.0 as outlined in the general procedure. Alkali metals, alkaline earths, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, UO₂²⁺, Te⁴⁺, Se⁴⁺ and Th⁴⁺ did not interfere with the estimation of copper. The ions such as Fe³⁺, Bi³⁺, Sb³⁺, Ti⁴⁺ and VO₃⁻ were effectively masked with tartaric acid (3.0 g). In the presence of MoO₄²⁻ and WO₄²⁻, the alcoholic concentration of the precipitation media was maintained at 50-60% by volume and the copper complex was washed with ethanol for several times. The partial hydrolysis of Sn⁴⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ was prevented by adding NaF or KF (2.5 g) and that of Ce⁴⁺ by ammonium sulphate (2 g). La³⁺ was tied up with ammonium acetate (2.5 g). Among anions, chloride, bromide, fluoride, borate, sulphate, acetate, oxalate, nitrate, arsenate and phosphate had no interfering effect on the determination. The results of the determinations are shown in Table 2.

TABLE-2 DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

(Copper taken = 12.00 mg ; pH, 3.9±0.1)

Diverse ions added (mg)	Weight of complex obtained (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Error % (mg)
Fe ³⁺ (60)	149.2	11.98	-0.16
Al ³⁺ (60)	149.6	12.2	+0.16
Cr ³⁺ (60)	149.4	12.02	Nil
Bi ³⁺ (50)*	149.3	11.99	-0.08
Sb ³⁺ (40)*	149.5	12.01	+0.08
Ni ²⁺ (50)	149.5	12.01	+0.08
Co ²⁺ (50)	149.3	11.99	+0.08
Mn ²⁺ (50)	149.5	12.01	-0.25
Hg ²⁺ (60)	149.1	11.97	+0.08
La ³⁺ (40)	149.8	12.03	+0.25
Ti ⁴⁺ (25)*	149.3	11.99	-0.08
Zr ⁴⁺ (40)(a)	149.3	11.99	-0.08
Tn ⁴⁺ (50)	149.2	11.98	-0.16
UO ₂ ²⁺ (40)	149.5	12.01	+0.08
VO ₃ ⁻ (30)*	149.5	12.01	+0.08
MoO ₄ ²⁻ (75)	149.6	12.02	+0.16
WO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	149.2	11.98	-0.16

* In presence of 3 g of tartaric acid in 125 ml of the solution
(a) In presence of 2.5 g of NaF.

Standard deviation : The relative standard deviation of the method for the determination of 12.00 mg of copper was ± 0.12% (x=30).

Determination of copper in alloys : To test the validity of the method three standard alloys obtained from Bureau of Analysed Samples, Ltd., Middlesbrough, Yorks, England were analysed for copper using the present reagent. The results summarised in Table 3 indicates that the proposed method gives precise and accurate results,

TABLE-3 DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN ALLOYS

Sample No. and name	Copper found* %	Certified value %	Standard deviation
8 c White metal	4.08	4.10	±0.014
5 f Brass	70.75	70.8	±0.060
6 f Gun metal	87.84	87.9	+0.074

a=average of 4 determinations

An accurately weighed amount of the alloy selected to provide 10-15 mg of copper in a 25 ml aliquot of the final solution was dissolved in 40% nitric acid. The solution was evaporated to a small volume and after dilution to 100 ml with water, precipitated tin and antimony oxides were filtered off. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with dilute nitric acid. The filtrate was again evaporated to near dryness and diluted with water. The solution was transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume. A 25 ml aliquot of the solution was pipetted in a 400 ml beaker and 1 g of tartaric acid was added. The amount of copper was determined following the recommended procedure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. G. Tandon, Head of the Chemistry Department, Ravishankar University, Raipur for providing research facilities

and to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of J.R.F. to one of us (K.S.P.).

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